

3rd Press Release | [August 2023](#)

Developing a guidance tool for implementing circularity in construction #1

RECONMATIC works on providing solutions to digitalize and automate construction and demolition waste management (CDWM) across construction domains and life cycle stages. To complement those solutions, the project is developing an open-source digital tool to guide the implementation and assessment of **circularity and sustainability practices** in different processes and stages of the life cycle of CDW.

The needs, gaps and opportunities of these solutions and the dimensions of circularity and sustainability that will be taken into account have already been identified. During August and September, interviews are being conducted with stakeholders in the construction sector to find out which features of the WP6 tool they consider relevant. We have the support of **designers and architects, contractors, manufacturers, asset managers, waste managers and demolition companies**. Many thanks to all of you that have already been in touch with us and provided valuable input.

The next step will be to go into detail to define the indicators that the guidance tool will take into account for its semi-quantitative assessment. During the next months, a **national workshop** will be organised by each country-member of the project consortium, inviting the sector's stakeholders to join them, in order to gain end-user insights to support the development of its features, through validating a selection of environmental, economic, social and circularity indicators that the tool will be based on as well as the assessment methodology used.

The workshop aims to ensure that this digital tool meets and adapts to their specific needs and interests, as end-users, in terms of circularity and sustainability. It will offer the participants the opportunity to network and collaborate with other stakeholders, interested in sustainability, as well as to be informed first-hand on sustainability solutions implemented and get insights on how to become more competitive in the construction industry.

If you are working in the construction life cycle and interested in applying circular economy practices, join us and help us develop a tool that meets your needs!

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Free registration here: <https://forms.gle/rewhqpf2tDtUeYhi9>

Your experience, expertise and active participation is essential in shaping the direction and success of this project and greatly appreciated!

Over the following months project news, publications and outputs will be available on the official project webpage at www.reconmatic.eu and distributed via the project social media channels on [LinkedIn](#) and Twitter [@reconmatic](#).

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